

MICROMECHANICAL DAMAGE SIMULATION OF FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO LOW VELOCITY IMPACT BY MULTI-SCALE METHOD

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ABSTRACT

An integrated multi-scale model was presented to simulate the fibre reinforced polymeric composite laminate subjected to low velocity impact. The multi-scale model was based on the embedded cell method, with detailed microstructure embedded into the macro laminate beneath the impact point, and a transition zone was introduced to link these two scales. Damage models were established for the fibres and matrix, and cohesive elements were used for the simulation of interface delamination. Both unidirectional and layup embedded cells were considered in the simulation so as to reveal the impact damage mechanisms from monolayer to layup levels. The simulation results indicate matrix cracking is the first damage form which occurs at the bottom of the laminate, and then delamination is induced when the matrix crack propagates to the interface, followed by fibre pull-out and fibre breakage. The simulation results are compared with available experimental results from literatures, and good agreements are achieved between them on the damage morphologies. Thus the ability of the presented multi-scale model to reveal the damage mechanisms of composite laminate under low velocity impact is validated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Low velocity impact is considered as one of the most dangerous damage sources of fibre reinforced polymeric composite structures, as it can cause significant reduction on the stiffness and strength of the structures, but the damage usually cannot be detected from the surface of the component, thus causing great security risks to the structures. For this reason, there have been a great number of researches on the low velocity impact damage of composites by both experimental and numerical approaches in the last decades. Recently, with the rapid development of computer power and finite element method (FEM), numerical simulation has gradually become an important method for the research of low velocity impact of composites.

During the low velocity impact process of composite laminates, various damage modes may occur simultaneously, including fibre breakage, matrix cracking, matrix crush and delamination. To take into account all these damage forms, the combination of continuum damage mechanics (CDM) and cohesive zone model (CZM) is often used to simulate the low velocity impact damage of laminates, and has achieved great success in the prediction of damage forms and damage extent of composite laminates subjected to low velocity impact [1]. However, these methods are based on the macro-scale, thus cannot capture the damage mechanisms at the micro-scale, including fibre/matrix debonding, fibre pull-out, and highly localized plastic deformation of the resin. On the other hand, though micro-mechanical simulations can capture these effects, they require high resolution mesh and significant computational power. Therefore, modeling of low velocity impact onto a composite at the micro-scale, capturing all these effects is currently and in the near future not feasible [2]. To overcome this contradiction between simulation accuracy and computational cost, an alternative is to use the multi-scale method taking into account the mechanical response at several length scales [3].

The wide range of multi-scale methods can be broadly classed into two groups: hierarchical and concurrent multi-scale methods. In hierarchical methods [4-5], a “one-way” bottom-up coupling is

established where information is passed from lower to higher scales. As a consequence, such methods are efficient in determining the macroscopic stiffness and strength of composites, but may have a limited predictive capability for problems involving damage [6]. Concurrent multi-scale methods [7-8] introduce the concept of scale embedding instead of scale transition, thus different scales coexist in adjacent regions of the model. This is especially useful for investigating impact events of composite laminates, since large deformations and damage are restricted to a local region. Thus only the damage zone requires a high resolution mesh, so that high simulation accuracy can be achieved with affordable computational cost.

Many researchers [9-12] have carried out multi-scale numerical simulation of the damage behavior of composite materials. However, all these studies were aimed at the quasi-static damage simulation of composites, thus are not applicable to the simulation of low velocity impact. Souza et al. [13] presented a multi-scale model for predicting damage evolution in composites due to impact loading. Yet, it was not a concurrent multi-scale model as information transfer was required between the global and local scale. Ha-Minh et al. [14] developed a numerical multi-scale model for textile woven fabric against ballistic impact, but the scale was limited to the mesoscopic level (yarns). May et al. [2] proposed an adaptive multi-scale methodology for modeling composites under high velocity impact. But the microscopic structure was not explicitly included in the model and the damage mechanisms were not discussed. So far, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there is not any research on the multi-scale modeling and simulation of fibre reinforced composites subjected to low velocity impact.

In this paper, an integrated multi-scale model based on finite element method will be developed for the simulation of fibre reinforced polymeric composite laminates subjected to low velocity impact. The micromechanical damage process of the composites will be discussed and compared with available experimental results, thus to provide a clear understanding of the micromechanical damage mechanisms of fibre reinforced composite laminates under low velocity impact.

2 MULTI-SCALE MODEL

In order to simulate the micromechanical damage behavior of composite laminates under low velocity impact with affordable computational cost, an integrated multi-scale model is required that contains both macro boundary conditions and microstructures of the damage zone. As the size of laminate is usually larger than the order of millimeter (length and width $\sim 10^1$ - 10^2 mm, thickness $\sim 10^0$ mm), while the dimension of constituents is in the order of micron (fibre diameter $\sim 10^0$ μm), it is impractical to use consistent mesh discretization for the whole model. Thus there should be a proper connection between these two scales. This can be accomplished by the embedded cell model [16], in which the full details of the composite microstructure are resolved in the region of interest, while the remaining part is represented as homogeneous material whose behavior is given by any suitable homogenization model.

For a composite laminate subjected to low velocity impact, it is well known that the region at the bottom of the laminate just under the impactor is most prone to suffer damage. Therefore, this area is selected as the region of interest where embedded cell with detailed microstructure is inserted, as shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the integrated multi-scale model under low velocity impact

The modeling and simulation platform of this study is the FEM package ABAQUS/Explicit, and tie constraint [16] provided in ABAQUS is used to accomplish the connection between the macro laminate and the micro embedded cell. However, as the tie constraint is a numerical connection technology, numerical error will be caused at the vicinity of the connecting surface. To avoid this issue, a transition zone is introduced between the macro laminate and the micro embedded cell, which will be further depicted in the following. The impactor is modeled as a hemispherical rigid body with an initial velocity in the vertical direction. The surface-to-surface contact algorithm is employed to simulate the contact between the impactor and the laminate, using a penalty formulation to take into account the effect of friction.

The size of the embedded cell can be determined according to the research requirement and computational power. In this paper, both unidirectional and layup embedded cells are used for the simulation. Shown in Fig.2 is the finite element model of the composite laminate with unidirectional embedded cell. The macro laminate is discretized by eight-node linear brick elements layer by layer, with gradually refined mesh from the edges to the central area. The embedded cell consists of polymeric matrix and randomly distributed fibres whose positions are determined by the RSE algorithm presented by the authors [17]. The transition zone can be divided into two parts: the two ends along the fibre direction contain microstructure of transitional fibres and matrix, with no material damage considered for them but ideal plastic behavior introduced instead to avoid unrealistic high stress; the rest is treated as equivalent composite material. Matching mesh is used for the transition zone and the embedded cell, while tie constraints are employed between the macro laminate and the transition zone. The size of the transition zone is properly determined by trial computation so that the boundary effect has little influence on the embedded cell. The whole model contains 40 fibres with volume fraction of 60% and a total of about 120,000 elements.

Figure 2: Finite element discretization of the multi-scale model with unidirectional embedded cell

Fig.3 illustrates the finite element model of the composite laminate with layup embedded cell. For simplicity, an orthotropic layup is used here. In order to model the delamination damage, a layer of cohesive elements are inserted between the two plies. The whole model contains about 400,000 elements. As the element length of the microstructure is quite small, a very small global stable time increment is resulted for the explicit solver. This will result in a very large number of analysis steps, which means unaffordable computational time. One possible solution for this problem is to use the mass scaling technology: by scaling the mass of the elements in the embedded cell and transition zone throughout the simulation, the stable time increment is increased and thus the computation time can be

significantly decreased. As the embedded cell and transition zone only account for a very small proportion of the whole model, increases in mass for these parts during the simulation will have little effect on the overall dynamic response.

Figure 3: Multi-scale model with layup embedded cell: (a) Partial cutaway view; (b) Embedded cell and transition zone

3 MICROMECHANICAL MATERIAL MODELS

The material chosen for the simulation is E-glass/epoxy composite from the World Wide Failure Exercise [18], in which the mechanical and thermal properties for both the laminae and the constitute materials are provided. The material models for the fibre, matrix and interlaminar layer are described briefly as below. For more details about the damage models of the material, readers please referred to [19].

3.1 Fibre

The E-glass fibre is considered to be isotropic material, the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of which are $E_f = 74$ GPa and $\nu_f = 0.2$. Since the fibre usually shows brittle characteristic, its damage behavior is controlled by the maximum stress criterion: once the stress exceeds the longitudinal tensile strength ($X_t = 2150$ MPa) of the fibre, failure is supposed to happen and the corresponding element is deleted from the model. The damage behavior of the fibres is achieved by writing a user subroutine VUMAT and implemented it into ABAQUS/Explicit.

3.2 Polymeric matrix

The polymeric matrix usually shows ductile characteristic and its mechanical behavior is sensitive to the hydrostatic stress. To capture these characteristics, the extended linear Drucker-Prager yield criterion is employed to predict the yielding of the matrix, which is expressed as follows [16]:

$$F = t - p \tan \beta - d = 0, \quad t = \frac{1}{2}q \left[1 + \frac{1}{k} - \left(1 - \frac{1}{k} \right) \left(\frac{r}{q} \right)^3 \right] \quad (1)$$

where p is the hydrostatic stress, q is the Mises equivalent stress, r is the third invariant of deviatoric stress, β is the slope of the linear yield surface in the p - t stress plane, d is the cohesion of the material, and k is the ratio of the yield stress in triaxial tension to that in triaxial compression and thus, introduces different yield behaviors between tension and compression.

The parameters in the equation, β , d and k can be determined by the following formulae:

$$\tan \beta = \frac{6 \sin \phi}{3 - \sin \phi} \quad (2)$$

$$d = \left(1 - \frac{1}{3} \tan \beta\right) \sigma_{mc} \quad (3)$$

$$k = \frac{3 - \sin \phi}{3 + \sin \phi} \quad (4)$$

where, ϕ is the internal friction angle of the material, which can be obtained from the tensile and compressive strength of the matrix:

$$\sin \phi = \frac{\sigma_{mc} - \sigma_{mt}}{\sigma_{mc} + \sigma_{mt}} \quad (5)$$

The elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of the epoxy matrix are $E_m = 3.35$ GPa and $\nu_m = 0.35$, and the tensile and compressive strengths are $\sigma_t = 80$ MPa and $\sigma_c = 120$ MPa. Substitute them into the above equations, then we have $\beta = 23.2^\circ$, $d = 103$ MPa, $k = 0.875$.

After yielding of the matrix, the ductile criterion is used for the prediction of damage onset, which assumes the equivalent plastic strain at the onset of damage, $\bar{\varepsilon}_D^{pl}$ is a function of stress triaxiality η ($\eta = -p/q$). The matrix is considered as ideal plastic, and the equivalent plastic strains at the onset of damage for uniaxial tension and compression are set as 0.05 and 0.5, respectively. Once damage is initiated, the damage evolution is controlled by a progressive failure procedure, which manifests itself in two forms: softening of the yield stress and degradation of the elasticity.

3.3 Interply interface

The interply interface is simulated by cohesive zone model, whose constitutive response is defined in terms of a bi-linear traction-separation law which relates the separation displacement between the top and bottom faces of the element to the traction vector acting upon it. The initial response is linear in absence of damage, and damage is assumed to initiate when the maximum nominal stress ratio reaches a value of one:

$$\max \left\{ \frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^0}, \frac{t_s}{t_s^0}, \frac{t_t}{t_t^0} \right\} = 1 \quad (6)$$

where t_n^0 , t_s^0 and t_t^0 represent the peak values of the nominal stress when the deformation is either purely normal to the interface or purely in the first or second shear direction, respectively. $\langle \rangle$ is the Macaulay brackets, which return the argument if positive and zero otherwise, thus to impede the development of damage when the interface is under compression.

Once the damage begins, the traction stress is reduced depending on the interface damage parameter, which evolves from 0 (in the absence of damage) to 1 (at ultimate failure). Since the interlaminar properties can hardly be measured from experiment, they are assumed to have similar mechanical properties with the matrix, i.e., the normal and the two shear strength of the interface are assumed to be equal to the tensile strength and the cohesion of the matrix, respectively: $t_n^0 = 80$ MPa, $t_s^0 = t_t^0 = 103$ MPa.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numerical simulations have been conducted for the low velocity impact of composite laminates using the proposed integrated multi-scale model. Firstly, unidirectional embedded cell is used to reveal the damage mechanisms of the laminate under low velocity impact at the monolayer level. And then layup embedded cell is adopted to include the effect of delamination. The simulation results will be discussed and compared with available experimental results in the following.

4.1 Unidirectional case

In order to get a clear understanding of the inducement of damage of the laminate under low velocity impact, the stress states of different sections of the laminate just before damage initiation (0.38 ms) are inspected separately, as shown in Fig.4. From Fig.4a we can see that due to the adoption of tie constraint, there is certain degree of stress mismatch between the macroscopic laminate and the microscopic cell at the connecting surface. But the introduction of transition zone can relieve this effect so that relatively real stress state is obtained inside the embedded cell. Fig.4b-d illustrates the stress fields of the transition zone and the fibres as well as the matrix of the embedded cell using different stress variables. To get a clear observation of the stress fields of the microstructures, only half of them are illustrated, with the transition zone cut at the z-x plane and the embedded cell cut at the y-z plane. As can be seen, stress is properly transferred from the transition zone to the fibres and matrix of the embedded cell. The fibres are all in tensile state, with axial stresses increasing from top to bottom. However, the maximum axial stress of the fibres is still much lower than the longitudinal tensile strength of the fibre, thus fibre breakage will not be induced. On the contrary, the maximum principal stress in the matrix has exceeded its tensile strength, especially at the bottom positions where two fibres are closely adjacent. Ductile damage has been triggered in these high stress regions, and matrix cracking will be induced at the point with the biggest damage factor in the following impact process, as marked in Fig.4e.

Figure 4: The stress fields of different sections of the laminate just before impact damage is initiated (0.38 ms): (a) Mises stress of the ensemble; (b) Mises stress of the transition zone; (c) Axial stress of the fibres; (d) Maximal principal stress of the matrix; (e) Ductile damage factor of the matrix

Fig.5 illustrates the simulated micromechanical damage initiation and evolution process of the unidirectional embedded cell during the impact event. As can be seen, matrix cracking first occurs at the locus as marked in Fig.4e, and rapidly propagates downward to the bottom surface. Meanwhile, the crack also propagates upward, but the propagating path is significantly influenced by the fibre distribution, forming a crooked crack surface, as shown in Fig.5a. With the proceeding of the impact event, the original crack surface continues to expand, and more dispersive matrix cracks are induced at different positions of the embedded cell, as shown in Fig.5b. Finally, fibre pull-out and breakage are observed at the bottom of the embedded cell, and matrix cracks have spread all over the embedded cell, as shown in Fig.5c.

Figure 5: Micromechanical damage initiation and evolution process of the unidirectional embedded cell under low velocity impact: (a) $t = 0.4$ ms; (b) $t = 0.74$ ms; (c) $t = 1.24$ ms

In order to verify the correctness of the multi-scale model, the simulation results are compared with available experimental results from the literature. Shown in Fig.6a is the fracture surface of E-glass/epoxy cross ply laminate ([0/90/0/90/0/90/0/90/0]) observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM) after low velocity impact [20]. Fig.6b-d are the simulated impact damage morphologies at different cross sections of the laminate. By comparison we can claim good agreements on damage morphology between the simulated results and experimental observation, including damage forms of matrix cracking and fibre/matrix debonding. Therefore, the ability of the presented multi-scale model in revealing the low velocity impact damage mechanisms of composite laminate is validated at the monolayer level.

Figure 6: Comparison of simulated impact damage at different cross sections with experimental result:
 (a) Experimental result [20]; (b) 1/4 section; (c) 1/2 section; (d) 3/4 section

4.2. Layup case

For the case of layup embedded cell, the stress fields of different sections of the laminate just before impact damage initiation (0.31 ms) are also examined, as shown in Fig.7. From Fig.7a we can see that all the fibres of both plies are in tensile state, with the stress increasing from top to bottom. But the stress in the fibres is still too small to induce fibre breakage. Fig.7b indicates high stress of the matrix at the bottom of the embedded cell where two fibres are closely adjacent, which is the direct cause of matrix cracking in the following impact process. Fig.7c illustrates the normal stress field of the interply interface at this moment. It can be seen that the interface is basically in compressive state, and local high compressive stress regions are formed at the intersections of the adjacent orthogonal fibres in upper and lower plies. Since compressive stress can suppress the occurrence of interlaminar damage, no delamination will be caused at this stress state.

Figure 7: The stress fields of different sections of the embedded cell just before impact damage is initiated (0.31 ms): (a) Axial stress of the fibres; (b) Max. principal stress of the matrix; (c) Normal stress of the interply interface; (d) Normal stress of the interface just before delamination (0.48 ms)

Fig.8 illustrates the simulated micromechanical damage initiation and evolution process of the layup embedded cell during the impact event. Firstly, matrix cracking occurs due to high tensile stress at the bottom of the embedded cell where two fibres are closely adjacent, and rapidly penetrates to the bottom surface, as shown in Fig.8a. Then, the original matrix crack gradually propagates upward, accompanied by the formation of more dispersive microcracks in the high tensile stress regions. When the front of the major crack approaches the interface, delamination is initiated, as shown in Fig.8b. The generation mechanisms of the delamination can be explained by Fig.7d, which illustrates the normal stress of the interface just before delamination is initiated. As can be seen, due to the approaching of the matrix crack, a tensile normal stress band is formed in the interface just above the matrix crack, while the rest of the interface is still in compressive state. It is the existence of this tensile normal stress band that causes the initiation of delamination. With the proceeding of impact, the area of delamination gradually increases and more matrix cracks happen in the lower ply of the embedded cell, as shown in Fig.8c. Finally, at impact time of 0.76 ms, matrix cracks have spread all over the lower ply, and delamination has propagated to almost the whole interface. Moreover, matrix cracks are also found in the upper ply, as shown in Fig.8d. But no fibre breakage has been induced at this impact time.

Figure 8: Micromechanical damage initiation and evolution process of the layup embedded cell under low velocity impact: (a) $t = 0.32$ ms; (b) $t = 0.49$ ms; (c) $t = 0.6$ ms; (d) $t = 0.76$ ms

The simulated damage initiation and evolution process at the central cross section of the embedded cell is inspected and compared with the SEM results given in [20], as shown in Fig.9. Fig.9a and b are the SEM results of the cross sections under the impact point of the laminate after low velocity impact, from which we can see the relationship between matrix cracks and delamination. Fig.9c-e are the simulated damage morphologies of the central cross section of the embedded cell at different impact time, from which we can obtain a clear understanding of the damage initiation and evolution process of the laminate under low velocity impact: matrix cracking is first initiated at the bottom of the lower ply; then the crack propagates upward in the ply; when the matrix crack reaches the interply interface, delamination is induced; finally the delamination propagates in the interface and more matrix cracks occur in the lower ply. By comparison we can conclude that good agreements are achieved between the simulated results and experimental observation. Therefore, the ability of the presented multi-scale model in revealing the low velocity impact damage mechanisms of composite laminate at the layup level is also validated.

Figure 9: Simulated impact damage initiation and evolution process at the central cross section of the embedded cell and comparison with experimental results: (a-b) SEM results [20]; (c) $t = 0.32$ ms; (d) $t = 0.49$ ms; (e) $t = 0.6$ ms; (f) $t = 0.76$ ms

5 CONCLUSIONS

A multi-scale numerical model is developed in this paper to investigate the damage behavior of fibre reinforced polymeric composite laminates subjected to low velocity impact. The multi-scale method is based on the embedded cell model, with the region of interest (for low velocity impact it is chosen as the bottom region of the laminate under the impact point) represented by details of the microstructure and the rest by homogeneous material. Transition zone is introduced to link the embedded cell to the macro laminate. Mass scaling technology is employed to speed up the numerical simulation. Both unidirectional and layup embedded cells are used to simulate the micromechanical damage process of composite laminate under low velocity impact, so as to reveal the micromechanical damage mechanisms of the laminate from monolayer to layup levels.

The simulation results indicate the damage process of the laminate under low velocity impact can be summarized as follows: matrix cracking is first initiated near the bottom of the laminate where two fibres are closely adjacent, and rapidly penetrates to the bottom surface; then the crack gradually propagates upward into the interior of the material, accompanied by the occurrence of more dispersed cracks; when the matrix crack reaches the interply interface, delamination is induced; after that both matrix cracks and delamination damage propagate continually during the following impact process; finally, fibre pull-out and fibre breakage happen at the bottom of the laminate. The simulation results are compared with available experimental results of literatures, and good agreements were achieved both in intraply and interply levels. Thus the validity of the presented multi-scale model is verified, and a comprehensive understanding of the damage mechanisms of composite laminate subjected to low velocity impact is accomplished.

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